

The Bass New Product Diffusion Model in Market Surveillance: Application in Forecasting the Spread of Substandard Consumer Goods

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Abstract—This paper presents the Bass New Product Diffusion Model as a market surveillance tool for estimating aspects related to the market penetration of substandard goods in the absence of sufficient data. It provides various illustrative cases and examples with respect to the applicability of the model in the field of market surveillance.

Index Terms—Bass Model, Market Surveillance, Substandard, Risk Management, Consumer, Economic Operator

I. INTRODUCTION

IN an unregulated or poorly regulated market, the Law of Demand results in a pull factor for trade in relatively lower-priced goods. The higher the price of an item, the less the demand for it by the Consumer. With price generally being construed by the Consumer as being directly proportional to quality (Day & Castleberry, 1986; Gavius & Lowengart, 2011), it follows that the higher the price, and hence the higher the quality of an item, the less the demand for it. In other words, Consumers are naturally inclined to purchase substandard goods, hence the term ‘quality aversion’ used to describe Consumer behaviour (Shake, 2018, p.2). On the supply side, the Law of Supply identifies profit as the primary push factor. Economic Operators will therefore supply lower priced (and hence lower quality) goods, in response to Consumer demand for lower priced goods, but this supply will be at increasing quantities in order to maximise on profits.

Lower quality goods are generally less durable and may also be unsafe. This results in a high turnover in terms of replacement by the Consumer, further increasing profits for the Economic Operators. From a game-theoretical point of view, this is a dominating strategy on the part of the Economic Operators (Shake, 2018, p.3). Consumers therefore require to be protected from substandard goods since, as a result of a natural force to maximise savings, they exhibit a predisposition towards purchasing substandard goods, a ‘weakness’ which is exploited by the Economic Operators driven by maximum profits.

To ensure that Consumers are accorded an effective and sustainable level of protection, Market Surveillance Authorities are mandated with, among others things, the removal or causing the removal of all substandard goods from circulation and providing Consumer Awareness on product quality requirements. In order to achieve this mandate of product

risk management, obtaining a clear view of the market with respect to the proliferation of substandard goods across space and time is both a vital requirement and objective of market surveillance.

In most instances, especially in developing regions, the information made available to Market Surveillance Authorities by Economic Operators with regard to product penetration is scant. This justifies the need for forecasting techniques in risk management decision making. Contemporary market surveillance lore, however, is silent on the subject of product diffusion analysis and forecasting techniques as tools in aiding risk management decision making. This article proposes the Bass New Product Diffusion Model as a robust tool to fill this void.

A. Definitions

The following are definitions for terms used in this article: *Market Surveillance* is defined as the activities carried out and measures taken by designated Market Surveillance Authorities (hereinafter, MSAs) to ensure that products in the market comply with the requirements set out in the relevant legislation and do not endanger health, safety or any other aspect of public interest protection (United Nations Economic Commission for Europe [UNECE], 2011, p. 22).

An *Economic Operator* (hereinafter, EO) is defined as the manufacturer, the authorised representative (acting on behalf) of the manufacturer, the importer or the distributor of any product in the market (UNECE, 2011, p. 8).

Quality means “how well something does what it is supposed to do, and is perceived in terms of in terms of construction, durability and performance” (Day & Castleberry, 1986). In the context of this paper, quality shall refer to compliance with set product standards and regulations in addition to the aforementioned understanding. Goods not meeting quality requirements shall be termed *substandard*.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A fairly sufficient background theory and mathematical derivation of the equations of the Bass Model can be found in the seminal paper by Bass (Bass, 1969). This article will therefore state and make use of the equations relevant to the discussion without delving into the depths of deriving them from first principles. The reader is encouraged to refer to the Bass paper (and any other relevant source) for the underlying theory and mathematical background to the Model.

The following Bass Model equations will be employed (Bass, 1969):

$$S(T) = pm + (q - p)Y(T) - \frac{q}{m}Y(T)^2 \quad (1)$$

$$S(T) = \left[m \frac{(p+q)^2}{p} \right] \times \left[\frac{e^{-(p+q)T}}{\left[\left(\frac{q}{p} \right) e^{-(p+q)T} + 1 \right]^2} \right] \quad (2)$$

$$T^* = \frac{\ln\left(\frac{q}{p}\right)}{p+q} \quad (3)$$

$$S(T^*) = \frac{m(p+q)^2}{4q} \quad (4)$$

$$Y(T^*) = \frac{m(q-p)}{2q} \quad (5)$$

$$E(T) = \frac{\ln\left[\frac{(p+q)}{p}\right]}{q} \quad (6)$$

where:

$S(T)$ is the number of new sales at time T (current rate of new sales),

$Y(T)$ is the cumulative number of buyers up to time T (number of previous buyers),

$E(T)$ is the expected time to purchase,

m is the market potential (the total number of available new buyers during the period of interest),

p is the coefficient of innovation, and

q is the coefficient of imitation.

Equation (1) is a polynomial equation of the form (Zakbar & Zuzel, 2002):

$$S(T) = aY(T)^2 + bY(T) + c \quad (7)$$

Regression analysis can be used to estimate Bass Model parameters since from Equations (1) and (7):

$$q = -ma \quad (8)$$

$$p = \frac{c}{m} \quad (9)$$

$$m = \frac{-b \pm \sqrt{b^2 - 4ac}}{2a} \quad (10)$$

Rearranging Equation (1) into a quadratic expression and solving for $Y(T)$, the number of previous buyers can therefore be expressed as:

$$Y(T) = \frac{(q-p) \pm \sqrt{\left[(q-p)^2 + 4\left(\frac{q}{m}\right)(pm - S(T)) \right]}}{2\left(\frac{q}{m}\right)} \quad (11)$$

III. OBJECTIVE

This paper explores the applicability of the Bass New Product Diffusion Model (hereinafter, Bass Model) as a tool for estimating and forecasting the spread of substandard consumer goods in the market.

IV. APPLICATION IN LIMITED-DATA CASES

A. Choice of the Bass Model Parameters

The Bass Model requires an evaluation of p , q and m parameters and using them for forecasting during the period of interest. These parameters can be obtained in three possible ways (Bass, 1969; Zakbar & Zuzel, 2002; Dekimpe et al. 1996):

- 1) Estimation of the parameters from time series data on current sales rates and cumulative sales following the discrete analogue to Equation (1).
- 2) Estimation of the parameters through regression analysis of data on current sales rates and cumulative sales (see Equations (7) to (10).
- 3) Using reported empirical results for average values of the parameters.

With respect to the illustrative examples given, this article concentrates on the third source for simplicity. The reader is however advised to refer to additional existing literature on the first two sources.

The mean value of the coefficient of innovation p for a new product is given as 0.001 for developed countries and 0.0003 for developing countries by Talukdar, Sudhir and Ainslie (2002, cited by Chandrasekaran & Tellis, 2007). Likewise the mean value of the coefficient of imitation for a new product q is given as 0.51 for developed countries and 0.56 for developing countries (Talukdar et al., 2002, cited by Chandrasekaran & Tellis, 2007). In contrast, Sultan, Farley and Lehmann (1990) proposed a mean value of 0.03 for p and a mean value of 0.38 for q . In this article we shall make use of the figures reported by Talukdar et al. (2002) chiefly because they are the more recent of the two sets.

B. Case 1: Elapsed Time Since Product Introduction and Current Sales Rate Known

Consider a scenario in which an EO has dumped an unknown quantity $Y(T)$ of goods in the market which the MSA has established to be substandard, and the only information made available to the MSA with respect to the goods is the time T that has elapsed since introduction of the goods into the market (either from the date of manufacture, importation or third-party procurement records) and the current rate of sales $S(T)$. This is a typical scenario facing MSAs especially with new products being introduced into the market.

One of the immediate risk management challenges in this case is to establish the possible volumes trading in the market, the position in time with respect to the product life cycle, and the level of diffusion or penetration in the market in order to identify the most effective risk mitigation.

Plugging in the respective values in Equation (3) gives average peak times T^* of around 13.4 'time periods' for developing countries and 12.2 'time periods' for developed countries. Comparing this information with the data related to the time of supply into the market provides an idea on the level of market penetration for a given product and gives the product's 'age' in terms of its life cycle.

In the absence of available data, a rule of thumb is proposed: the value of m for a given product can be estimated by taking

into account the product type and the portion of the population the product is intended for. For example, m in the case of a toy meant for children under the age of three in a given region can be safely estimated to be the population of children under the age of three in the said region.

With p , q , m and $S(T)$ known, the next step is to evaluate $Y(T)$ by solving for the two possible solutions in Equation (11). In order to establish the correct solution from the pair, a comparison between the value of T provided by the MSA and the value of T^* obtained from Equation (3) will be made:

- 1) If T is less than T^* then the smaller value $Y(T)$ is the correct solution.
- 2) If T is greater than T^* then the bigger value of $Y(T)$ is the correct solution.
- 3) If T is equal to T^* then both values of $Y(T)$ will be equal (there is only one solution of $Y(T)$).

1) *Illustrative Example:* Consider, for illustrative purposes, the RAPEX Alert No. A12/1477/18 issued by Cyprus on the *Cute Baby* plastic doll, and further consider a situation in which the product is found at an EO during a random market surveillance inspection activity. On enquiry the MSA inspectors are informed that the current sales rate is 1,000 dolls per day. The EO further states that they are the sole importer and distributor of the toy in the market, and that the product has been in the market for three days. The following are the assumptions made:

- 1) The toy is accessible to children under the age of three (disregarding the applicable-age warning on the packaging), and
- 2) The number of children in Cyprus below the age of three is 40,000.

Taking p as 0.001, q as 0.51, m as 40,000 and $S(T)$ as 1,000 and plugging these values into Equation (11) gives $Y(T)$ as 926 and 37,938. Similarly, from Equation (3) $T^*=12.2$. Noting that $T=3$ is less than $T^*=12.2$, the correct value for $Y(T)$ is thus 926.

Note also that Equation (2) provides a means of verifying the value of T provided by the EO by plugging in the known values for p , q , m and $S(T)$ and solving for T . In this case two values of T are obtained for which $S(T)$ is 1,000: 6.5 days and 17.9 days, which indicates that the value of 3 provided by the EO in this hypothetical case is incorrect.

C. Case 2: Only Elapsed Time Since Product Introduction Known

Consider a scenario in which the only information provided to the MSA is the time T that has elapsed since introduction of goods established to be substandard into the market. The challenge is to establish the possible cumulative quantities that have been sold up to that moment in time.

With p , q , m and T known or established as described in the preceding scenario, $S(T)$ can be evaluated using Equation (2), the value of which can be plugged into Equation (11) to obtain the correct value for $Y(T)$ following the method described in the first scenario.

1) *Illustrative Example:* Consider the example given in the preceding section, but modified in this case such that the only information the EO has provided to the MSA is the time that has elapsed since the introduction of the toys into the market (three days).

Taking p as 0.001, q as 0.51, m as 40,000 and plugging these values into Equation (2) gives $S(T)$ as 183. Plugging this information into Equation (11) gives $Y(T)$ as 283 and 19,687. Similarly, from Equation (3) $T^*=12.2$. Noting that $T=3$ is less than $T^*=12.2$, the correct value for $Y(T)$ is thus 283.

D. Case 3: Only Current Sales Rate Known

Consider a scenario in which only the current rate of sales $S(T)$ of goods established to be substandard is known. The challenge is to establish the possible cumulative quantities that have been sold up to that moment in time.

With p , q , m and $S(T)$ known or established as described in the preceding scenario, Equation (11) can be used to obtain the correct value for $Y(T)$ following the method described in the first scenario. T can be evaluated using Equation (2).

1) *Illustrative Example:* Consider the example given in the preceding section, but modified in this case such that the only information the EO has provided to the MSA is the current rate of sales $S(T)$, 1,000 dolls per day.

Taking p as 0.001, q as 0.51, m as 40,000 and $S(T)$ as 1,000 and plugging these values into Equation (11) gives $Y(T)$ as 926 and 37,938. As described in the first scenario, the value of T is obtained by plugging in the known values for p , q , m and $S(T)$ and solving for T . In this case two values of T are obtained for which $S(T)$ is 1,000: 6.5 days and 17.9 days.

V. LIMITATION OF THE BASS MODEL

The Bass Model assumes a static market potential with respect to time. This may be reasonably representative of the facts in the short to medium term. However, the market potential is a function of time because the population, and hence the number of potential new buyers, tends to change with time.

While this assumption is a potential source of deviation from empirical results, research has shown close conformity of the Bass Model with empirical data (Bass, 1969; Bass, Krishnan & Jain, 1994; Zakbar & Zuzel, 2002; Dekimpe et al., 1996). This suggests that the contribution due to normal population change is negligible across the product life cycle.

VI. CONCLUSION

It has been shown that the Bass Model is a useful tool for estimating the volumes trading in the market at any given point in time, the current rate of sales given the elapsed time since product introduction, the elapsed time given the current rate of sales and other consequent parameters. The critical inputs required for the Model are the coefficient of innovation p , the coefficient of imitation q , the market potential m and the time T that has elapsed since introduction of goods established to be substandard into the market.

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